

Generalized Median Computation for Consensus Learning: A Brief Survey

Xiaoyi Jiang¹ and Andreas Nienkötter²

¹ Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Münster, Münster, Germany

² Institute for Disaster Management and Reconstruction, Sichuan University-Hongkong Polytechnic University, Chengdu, Sichuan, China

Abstract. Computing a consensus object from a set of given objects is a core problem in machine learning and pattern recognition. A popular approach is the formulation of generalized median as an optimization problem. The concept of generalized median has been studied for numerous problem domains with a broad range of applications. Currently, the research is widely scattered in the literature and no comprehensive survey is available. This brief survey contributes to closing this gap and systematically discusses the relevant issues of generalized median computation. In particular, we present a taxonomy of computation frameworks and methods. We also outline a number of future research directions.

1 Introduction

Given a set of objects $O = \{o_1, \dots, o_n\}$ in domain \mathcal{D} with an associated distance function $\delta : \mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$, a common approach to consensus learning is to find the so-called *Generalized Median* (GM):

$$\bar{o} = \arg \min_{o \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{o_i \in O} \delta(o, o_i) = \arg \min_{o \in \mathcal{D}} \Omega_O(o) \quad (1)$$

where $\Omega_O(o)$ is the sum of distance between o and set O . Note that the GM object is not necessarily part of set O or even unique. Intuitively, the GM represents a formalized averaging or consensus (prototype) learning. In addition, it can also be understood as a specific form of ensemble solution.

Generally, GM computation is performed in two ways: 1) **Data aggregation:** The input data are aggregated to receive the final result, e.g. image smoothing [40] and atlas construction [45]. 2) **Output aggregation:** The input data are first processed to obtain n results. These base results are then aggregated to obtain the final result. Examples are consensus clustering [3] and image segmentation fusion [22,27] that help to reduce the uncertainty of the initial solutions for more robustness, e.g. for boosting low precision segmentation models.

GM computation has found numerous applications in many fields. For instance, consensus ranking is of common interest to bioinformatics, social sciences, and complex network analysis [39]. Averaging 3D rotations has been intensively

studied for computer vision, mixed reality, and computer-assisted surgery [42]. Averaging quaternions is interesting for astronautics [28]. Ensemble clustering has strong potential for pattern recognition, it is also omnipresent in computer vision [44], e.g. in bag-of-words models. Biclustering is fundamental to bioinformatics [46]. Other applications include robust and nonlinear subspace learning [5] and deep neural network for manifold-valued data [6]. Further examples can be found in [36]. Generally, GM computation makes the centroid based clustering algorithms such as K-means applicable to arbitrary domains, thus contributing to one of the most studied unsupervised machine learning tasks.

Currently, the vast number of research papers are widely scattered in the literature. While there are a few survey papers on specific topics (e.g. strings [34], clusterings [3]), no comprehensive discussion is available yet. In this paper we systematically discuss all relevant issues of GM computation. In particular, we made substantial efforts to identify common algorithmic design patterns, which leads to a taxonomy of computation frameworks and methods.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. We first consider theoretical aspects of GM computation in Section 2. The taxonomy is presented in Section 3, followed by a detailed discussion of domain-independent computation frameworks and methods in Section 4. We sketch further variants of GM computation in Section 5. Finally, we conclude our paper by future research directions.

2 Theoretical considerations of GM computation

A statistical interpretation of GM as maximum-likelihood estimator is shown recently [36]. In the following we elaborate further important theoretical issues.

Computational complexity. The efforts needed to compute the GM differ considerably. In the simplest case, when averaging x_1, \dots, x_n , $x_i \in \mathbb{R}$ (a well-known concept from statistics), two popular distance functions are: $\delta(x, y) = (x - y)^p$, $p = 1, 2$. The GM is the arithmetic average of the given numbers ($p = 2$) and the median ($p = 1$). The related computational complexity is $\mathcal{O}(n)$ in both cases. Analytical solutions, e.g. [15], often have low polynomial complexity. Efficient solutions can also be given by favorable convergence behavior of iterative approaches (e.g. Weiszfeld algorithm [2], see Section 4).

Despite the simple definition in Eq. (1), many problem instances of GM computation turn out to be \mathcal{NP} -hard. A number of papers are concerned with such complexity proofs. Examples include strings using the edit distance [17], rankings with the popular Kendall- τ distance [4], consensus clustering for many common distance functions, e.g. the Mirkin-metric [23], as well as graphs [8] and signed permutations [1] using common distance functions.

Bounds. A lower bound Γ of the sum of distance is a value: $0 \leq \Gamma \leq \Omega(\bar{o})$. A trivial lower bound is zero, which is however useless. Generally, Γ should be as tight as possible, ideally equal to $\Omega(\bar{o})$.

Due to the inherent hardness many algorithms for GM computation are of approximate nature so that there is no guarantee to obtain the optimal solution. Since the genuine GM is unknown, a practical way to assess the quality of a

Fig. 1: Taxonomy of domain-independent GM computation methods.

computed GM o is given by $\Delta = (\Omega(o) - \Gamma)/\Gamma$ [36]. In particular, if $\Delta \approx 0$, then it can be safely claimed that there is hardly room for further improvement. This can, for instance, be used to stop an iterative search for the GM or performance evaluation of algorithms. On the other hand, in case of large Δ , we must be careful in making any claims. The large deviation may be caused by two reasons: The lower bound is not tight enough in that particular case or the computed solution o is still far away from the (unknown) optimal solution \bar{o} .

A few lower bounds are available in general case of metric spaces. The lower bound from [20] can be efficiently solved by maximum weight matching. Another lower bound from [19] is based on linear programming with $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ constraints. Domain-specific lower bounds exist as well, e.g. [14] for consensus clustering using Merkin distance, which should be more tight than general, domain-independent lower bounds.

Given the GM solution \bar{o}^* found by some algorithm, an upper bound Γ^* : $\Omega(\bar{o}) \leq \Omega(\bar{o}^*) \leq \Gamma^*$ provides a quality guarantee for \bar{o}^* . An example is given in Section 5. Note that the lower bound is a statement for a GM problem instance while the upper bound is related to a particular algorithm for its solution.

3 Taxonomy of GM computation

The variety of computational frameworks and algorithms can be viewed from different perspectives: domain-specific or independent, continuous or discrete space, requirement of metric space or not, exact or approximate solution. Among these distinctions, we will distinguish between domain-specific and independent approaches and focus on the latter one. While touching other issues where appreciate, our discussion will follow common algorithmic design patterns.

The nature of many domain-specific solutions is typically strongly determined by the domain's specific characteristics and thus often cannot be easily transferred to other domains. For instance, [40] is dedicated to fast algorithms for filtering of signals and images with values on the unit circle based on the arc distance median. In string space an elegant dynamic programming technique is well-known for computing the Levenshtein edit distance. It can be extended to exactly compute the median string [24]. With $\mathcal{O}(L^n)$ ($\mathcal{O}(L)$: string length) for both time and space requirement, however, its applicability is restricted to small sets and short strings only. If the sum of distances $\Omega(\hat{o})$ is guaranteed to lie

under some (relatively small) upper bound, then the computational expense can be reduced significantly [26], although remaining exponential.

4 Domain-independent frameworks and methods

Most of the domain-independent GM computation methods can be divided into five categories that are presented in the taxonomy in Figure 1.

Greedy methods. The problem-solving heuristic greedy makes the locally optimal decision at each stage. It is particularly easy to apply it, for instance, to domains \mathcal{D} , where the objects have a linear structure and the GM computation can thus be naturally divided into stages. This is the case in string space. Starting from an empty string, the greedy algorithm [25] constructs an approximate median string symbol by symbol.

Iterative refinement. Several strategies of iterative refinement are known. They mainly differ in the kind of operations that are performed in the iterations.

a) Perturbation methods. Starting from an initial solution, perturbation methods modify the current solution by using base operations to possibly obtain an improved one. This perturbation step is repeated until convergence. A good option to obtain an initial solution is the set median, see Section 5. In string space [32] systematically changes the current string by performing the edit operations insertion, deletion, and substitution in every position. For consensus clustering [13] goes through the data items and considers placing them into a different cluster or creating a new singleton cluster. Each data item is placed in the cluster that yields the minimum sum of distances $\Omega(o)$. The iterative refinement terminates if there is no move that can improve the cost.

b) Combination methods. Iterative pairwise averaging is a possible way of combination. Starting from the input set O , it iteratively replaces two objects from the current set by their combination. The main differences between existing methods are the order in which the combinations are performed and the way they compute a combination (average) of two objects, see discussions in [38]. The simplest ordering consists in pairwise averaging objects following a tournament scheme. That is, $n/2$ average objects are generated in the first iteration. Then, the next iterations further reduce the number of remaining objects by factor 2 until reaching a singleton set. In this approach, the averaging method (between two objects) is applied n times.

Mathematical optimization. The GM computation as formulated in Eq. (1) can be solved by continuous and discrete mathematical optimization techniques.

a) Optimization in continuous spaces. For a continuous space $\mathcal{D} = \mathbb{R}^d$, the GM problem becomes a continuous optimization: $\min_{o=(x_1, \dots, x_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d} \Omega(o)$. It either has an analytic solution or has to be solved by some iterative optimization method. Both situations occur, for instance, in single rotation averaging [15], dependent on the choice of distance function.

Care must be taken if the objects of interest do not cover the complete \mathbb{R}^d , but some subspace $\mathcal{D}^* \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ only. Then, the optimization above needs to be

constrained to \mathcal{D}^* . This can range from rather easy computation, e.g. by means of a suitable representation (e.g. quaternion for 3D rotation [15]), to very complex manifold handling (e.g. atlas construction in image space [45]).

Other methods exist for optimization in continuous spaces. In [41] consensus clustering is recast into a problem of probabilistic model of consensus and solved by the EM algorithm. This work is also an interesting case of transforming a discrete problem (label assignment) into a continuous (probabilistic) one.

b) Optimization in discrete spaces. Numerous GM problems are of discrete nature. Here different techniques of discrete optimization come into play. For instance, [16] solves the problem of median string computation based on the Levenshtein distance by using integer linear programming.

Search space exploration. This class of methods perform a search in the solution space. The different methods mainly vary in the way of candidate generation. The goodness of solution candidates can be measured by means of Ω .

a) Evolutionary methods. Evolutionary methods are a family of algorithms for global optimization inspired by biological evolution. They are typically based on evolving populations of solutions, where operators are applied to modify members of the population subject to natural selection and mutation rules. Since not every encoding corresponds to a valid solution in general, the generated solutions often need to be post-processed to become valid ones. A genetic algorithm has been designed to compute median graph [20]. Consensus clustering has been tackled using several evolutionary methods, including genetic algorithm [7], particle swarm optimization [37], and simulated annealing [43].

b) Constrained search space exploration. The search space for GM computation is huge in general. It thus makes sense to constrain the search as much as possible by using knowledge, either general or specific to the problem domain. An example of the former case is the approach in [11]. It uses a domain-independent lower bound (see Section 2) to considerably prune the search space for candidate generation.

Space transformation. This class of methods solve the optimization problem not in the original space \mathcal{D} , but in a new space after a suitable transformation. A key issue here is the inverse transformation back to \mathcal{D} .

a) Representation space averaging. This class of methods consist of three steps: 1) Transform of objects from \mathcal{O} in space \mathcal{D} into a representation space; 2) Performing an averaging in the representation space; 3) Determine an object in space \mathcal{D} that fits the average in the representation space well.

The influential work on consensus clustering [12] and its variants (e.g. [30]) are representative for representation space averaging techniques. A clustering of a dataset with m data items is described by a $m \times m$ matrix C , where $C(i, j)$, $1 \leq i, j \leq m$, is 1 if the pattern pair (i, j) is assigned to the same cluster and 0 otherwise. Given n clusterings of the dataset with the related matrices C_k , $1 \leq k \leq n$, the average co-association matrix is simply $\bar{C} = 1/n \sum_{k=1}^n C_k$. A final clustering is constructed that corresponds to \bar{C} or fits \bar{C} at best. In [12] this is realized by applying a hierarchical agglomerative clustering algorithm using \bar{C}

as similarity matrix. This approach can be easily extended to achieve fuzzy consensus clustering [3]. Given a consensus similarity matrix \bar{C} , the final clustering can also be generated using graph-based approaches [3].

b) Vector space embedding. The vector space embedding method has received considerable attention and has been shown to successfully solve a number of \mathcal{NP} -hard consensus learning problem instances with superior performance. It consists of three steps: 1) Embedding of objects from O into Euclidean vector space; 2) Computation of geometric median by Weiszfeld algorithm [2]; 3) Reconstruction of approximate median in the original space.

The embedding was initially suggested to be done by means of a number of selected prototypes $p_1, \dots, p_d \in O$ [9]: $\phi(o_i) = (\delta(o_i, p_1), \delta(o_i, p_2), \dots, \delta(o_i, p_d))$. This embedding function, however, bears a number of drawbacks, in particular violating the highly desired distance preservation, i.e. $\phi_e(\phi(o_i), \phi(o_j)) = c \cdot \delta(o_i, o_j)$, $\forall 1 \leq i, j \leq n$, $c > 0$, with $\phi_e()$ being the Euclidean distance. An extensive empirical study [35] demonstrated significantly improved quality of GM computation using distance-preserving embedding methods (e.g. Sammon mapping and curvilinear component analysis). The recent work [36] proposes a novel kernel approach by using an *implicit* transformation in terms of kernel functions. It turns out to be possible to handle the GM computation *without* knowing the dimension of the embedded space and the concrete embedding.

The last step to transform the Euclidean median from vector space back into the original space is a special instance of the pre-image problem in machine learning [18]. Several reconstruction methods can be found in [9].

Representation space averaging and vector space embedding are instances of space transformation techniques. In the former case the representation space can be arbitrary and has a natural “semantical” interpretation. In contrast, the vector space is an abstract space for mathematical mapping only.

c) Kernel-based methods. Although dedicated to consensus clustering, the method in [43] is in fact generally valid for arbitrary domains. If the distance function δ is a positive semi-definite kernel, the input objects can be implicitly mapped to the corresponding reproducing kernel Hilbert space. Then, the GM results from an inverse transformation of the average object in that space by solving a pre-image problem. Despite the implicit nature of the mapping, the kernel trick leads to an optimization problem using the original objects only. This optimization task is not trivial and solved by simulated annealing in [43].

Discussions. The various categories of methods discussed above differ in their nature. While optimization in continuous space and vector space embedding are examples of concrete algorithms, many others are algorithmic design frameworks only and need to be concretized by domain-specific details.

In practice the greedy strategy and iterative refinement can yield suboptimal solutions efficiently, but are typically not appropriate for high-quality GM computation. Perturbation methods may serve as a means of post-processing to further improve an approximate solution found by more sophisticated methods. In addition, they can be used for local search to enhance the quality of populations in evolutionary methods. Techniques of search space exploration and space

transformation are powerful tools in general and have demonstrated their ability in a variety of highly-complex GM computation problems.

5 Variants of GM Computation

Set median. This related concept, also known as medoid, results from an optimization of (1) restricting the search space to O instead of the complete domain \mathcal{D} . The set median may serve as an approximative solution for the GM, which is justified by the fact (upper bound) $\Omega(o^*) \leq (2 - 2/n) \cdot \Omega(\bar{o})$, where o^* represents the set median [34].

A naive computation of set median requires $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ distance computations, which is inappropriate in spaces with high computational cost of each individual distance (e.g. strings, graphs), especially in case of a large number of objects. This computational burden can be reduced in metric spaces [21]. For non-metric spaces an approximate set median can be efficiently estimated [31].

Weighted GM. The definition of GM in (1) can be extended to a weighted one: $\bar{o} = \arg \min_{o \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{o_i \in O} w_i \cdot \delta(o, o_i)$. The weight w_i represents the estimated merit of object o_i . The recent review [47] discusses weighted consensus clustering including major approaches to determining the weights. An extension of the linear programming based lower bound [19] to this weighted case is straightforward.

Center object. The center object of $O = \{o_1, \dots, o_n\}$ in domain \mathcal{D} is an object \bar{o} whose distance δ to all o_i is at most r , while r is chosen to be minimal:

$$\min_{\bar{o}, r} \quad r, \quad \text{subject to } \delta(o_i, \bar{o}) \leq r, \quad \forall o_i \in O$$

The particular problem instance in string space, also termed as closest string, has many applications in computational biology and coding theory. The computation of the closest string turns out to be \mathcal{NP} -hard for many metrics, including Hamming distance for strings of equal length. The embedding framework has been adapted to solve this problem [33], not limited to strings.

6 Future directions

In this section we sketch some directions for stimulating future research.

Formalization. While numerous works follow the formal definition (1), others are based on informal approaches. Many of such works, however, can be recast into this formal framework by a transformation into a representation space. It will be helpful to identify this recast in as many methods as possible so that they can benefit from all available theoretical results in this formal framework.

Theoretical considerations. Although generally applicable, domain-independent lower bounds may not be tight enough for a particular domain. There are still very few domain-specific lower bounds yet. The concept of breakdown point from robust statistics [29] is useful for studying robustness for GM computation in case of outliers. So far only special spaces, e.g. Riemannian manifolds [10],

have been considered and there is a lack of studies on breakdown point and further robustness issues in a general setting.

Methodological development. There is still lot of room for developing additional general frameworks or methods and also domain-specific solutions. In addition, algorithmic considerations should also cover aspects that are largely neglected so far. An example is robust GM computation to tolerate outliers. Manifold handling is generally challenging [45]. Currently, very few works have an integrated manifold handling although it may be required in many cases.

Public domain resources and benchmarking. The published methods typically do not provide their code for public use. There is still very few publicly available software for GM computation. There are hardly any benchmarking resources available in the community. This is even true for such extensively studied topics like consensus clustering. Large-scale public datasets are lacking, also (possibly synthetic) datasets with known ground truth for quantitative performance evaluation. Large-scale benchmarking studies, e.g. organized in the form of contests, will help to obtain a comprehensive overview of the state of the art.

Domain extensions and applications. The concept of GM is universal and can be introduced to a broader range of problem domains. In addition, the existing methods can be integrated into even more applications.

7 Conclusion

The formal approach (1) to GM computation has many advantages. As soon as formulated within this framework, one can benefit from all theoretical results and computation methods available in the literature. This leads to conceptual clarity, comprehensive understanding of computation, and ease of problem solving. In this paper we have presented a brief survey of GM computation, which is to our best knowledge the first one in the literature. Particularly, we have identified several future research directions. With this survey we contribute to further development of this fascinating research area with huge potential of theoretical and algorithmic development as well as applications in virtually all domains.

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